

Impact of climate smart agriculture adoption on food security: The case of urban market gardeners in the city of Réo, Burkina Faso

Nadège Compaoré¹, Joseph Yaméogo^{*1,2}

¹Norbert Zongo University, Department of Geography, Koudougou, Burkina Faso

²Postdoc African Cluster Centers of Joseph Ki-Zerbo University, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso

Article published on September 03, 2024

Key words: Smart strategies, Variability of rainfall, Food security, City of Réo, Burkina Faso

Abstract

Climate change is affecting Burkina Faso's cities. This situation is forcing urban dwellers to take innovative measures to adapt. Several smart strategies have been implemented in urban market gardening to cope with recent rainfall variability over the period 2001-2021. The main objective of the study is to analyze the changes in rainfall in the area, the smart strategies used and the consequences in terms of food security of the strategies promoted in urban market gardening in Réo. To achieve this, a methodology combining secondary and primary data was required. Descriptive statistics, linear and logistic regression and the rainfall concentration index (PCI) were used to process the data collected. The study showed that the area has a high variability, with a PCI >20, reflecting a high variability and concentration of rainfall over a few months. In addition, the cumulative annual rainfall is increasing over the decade 2001-2021. This situation forces farmers to adopt a number of intelligent strategies to deal with the situation. This has led to leafy vegetable production, multi-species integration in vegetable plots and the introduction of short-cycle vegetables. These strategies have led to an increase in dietary diversity and a high level of food consumption, which has had an impact on the food security of market gardeners. The level of food insecurity is also low. This shows that the smart strategies promoted in the garden plots lead to high levels of food security for the market gardeners.

*Corresponding Author: Joseph Yaméogo ✉ josephyameogo10@gmail.com

Introduction

Climate variability refers to variations in the mean state and other statistics (such as standard deviations, occurrence of extremes) of the climate on all time scales (IPCC, 2022). It affects every continent in the world and Africa is no exception (IPCC, 2021). In West Africa, changes in precipitation are long-run trends (Lüning *et al.*, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In the Sahelian zone of West Africa, the Sahelian rainfall regime is characterised by a persistent deficit in the number of rainy days. At the same time, the frequency of extreme rainfall events has increased between 1970 and 2010 (Panthou *et al.*, 2014). The proportion of annual precipitation associated with extreme precipitation increased from 17 % in 1970 to 1990, to 18.9 % in 1991 to 2000, and to 21 % in 2001 to 2010 (Panthou *et al.*, 2014).

Sylla *et al.* (2016) suggest that West Africa will experience shorter rainy seasons, widespread arid and semi-arid conditions, longer dry spells and more intense extreme precipitation. In the face of this situation, smart agriculture has been identified by international organizations as a solution (Finizola *et al.*, 2024). This is because it is a key strategy to ensure the sustainability of agricultural systems and to guarantee food security and nutrition in the context of a changing climate (Antwi and Antwi-Agyei, 2023). Consequently, the issue is the subject of research in many countries around the world. Studies have been conducted in India (Kaur *et al.*, 2023; Agarwal *et al.*, 2022), Indonesia (Luckyardi *et al.*, 2022) and Bangladesh (Hasn *et al.*, 2018). In Africa, the majority of studies on climate-smart strategies have focused on East Africa. Studies focus on the drivers of smart agriculture adoption in Malawi (Shani *et al.*, 2024), Ethiopia (Zelege *et al.*, 2024) and Kenya (Ndung'u *et al.*, 2023). Other studies explore the impact of smart strategies on livelihoods (Tilahun *et al.*, 2023) and food security in South Africa (Abegunde *et al.*, 2022).

However, there are few studies in the Sahel region of West Africa, such as in Burkina Faso. Several studies in the north and south-west (Yanogo and Yaméogo,

2023), in the Mouhoun loop (Rouamba *et al.*, 2023) and in the west (Sougoué *et al.*, 2023) show an increase in extreme rainfall between 1980 and 2020. In urban areas, however, the situation will be critical, as extreme precipitation trends will increase over the period 2020-2040 (Yaméogo, 2024). The integration of smart strategies has become an important necessity for urban dwellers. In Burkina Faso's cities, people are opting to change their socio-economic activities, as in the city of Réo, in the province of Sanguié, in the centre-west of Burkina Faso. The town is criss-crossed by many low-lying areas. The inhabitants take advantage of these natural conditions to grow vegetables in the town. However, the variability of rainfall forces them to reorganize the cultivation systems on their plots (Yanogo, 2023). In order to cope with the current rainfall conditions, this situation forces the gardeners to adopt a variety of smart strategies in the garden plots. The main objective of the study is therefore to analyze the changes in rainfall in the area, the smart strategies used and the consequences in terms of food security of the strategies promoted in urban market gardening in Réo.

Materials and methods

Presentation of the study area

The commune of Réo covers an area of approximately 432 km². It is subdivided into nine (09) sectors (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Geographical location of the study area

The town of Réo is part of the Réo district. It is a town with a population of about 33,894 distributed over 9 sectors and several villages. The study area is located

in sector 9 of Réo, with more than 30,000 inhabitants in 2019, including 7,676 in sector 9, the study area.

Data from the study

There are secondary and primary data. The secondary data come from the rainfall records of the Réo station in the province of Boulkiemdé, in the Centre-West region. They cover the period 2001-2021. They were obtained from the National Meteorological Agency of Burkina Faso. This period was chosen because there are no rainfall records from the Réo station. There are other stations, but they are not close to where we want to study. There are other stations, but they are not close to the study area and their inclusion could distort the results, hence the choice of the only station that allows an adequate assessment of the climatic situation in the area.

The primary data were obtained using the survey method. Purposive sampling is the sampling technique used in this study. The survey form was distributed to market gardeners in sector 9 of Réo. The size of the household to be interviewed was determined using Fisher's formula as follows:

$$N = \frac{t^2 \cdot p(1 - p)}{e^2} \tag{1}$$

Where,

N= represents the target population to be studied;

t: 95% confidence level (standard value 1.96);

p: is the proportion of market gardeners in the town of Réo. It is estimated at 14.6%.

e: the margin of error at 5% (standard value 0.05).

The application of the formula gives N = 192.08, i.e. N = 192 market gardeners to be interviewed. The survey forms were drawn up for the surveys carried out in sector 9 of Réo between December 2023 and February 2024, i.e. three (03) months.

Methods of data processing and analysis

These are based on secondary data from precipitation data and primary data from field surveys. The secondary data processing and analysis methods are based on SPI, linear regression and precipitation concentration index to characterize precipitation in the study area.

Standardized precipitation index (SPI)

This is used to quantify precipitation deficit on different time scales (Balram and Fanai, 2020) (Table 1).

$$SPI = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \left(\frac{P_j^i - P_j^-}{\sigma_j} \right) \tag{2}$$

Where, P_j^i is the rainfall in year i at station j , P_j the interannual mean rainfall at station j , σ_j the standard deviation of the seasonal cumulative series at station j , and N_i the number of stations in year i .

Table 1. Interpretation of drought level

Valeur SPI	Level of dryness
$SPI \geq 2,0$	Extremely wet
$1,5 \leq SPI < 2,0$	Very wet
$1,0 \leq SPI < 1,5$	Moderate humidity
$- 1,0 \leq SPI < 1,0$	Normal
$- 1,5 \leq SPI < - 1,0$	Moderate drought
$- 2,0 \leq SPI < - 1,5$	Severe drought
$- 2,0 \leq SPI$	Extreme drought

Source: McKee *et al.*, 1993

Linear regression method

It is a parametric test that determines the relationship between two or more dependent and independent variables that have a causal relationship (Atilgan *et al.*, 2017). The hypothesis assumes that there is a linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables, so linear regression is defined as follows (El-Geziry, 2022; Yaméogo and sawadogo, 2024):

$$Y = \alpha + bX \tag{3}$$

Where, Y indicates a dependent variable, X indicates an independent variable, and a is the slope of the line and b is the y-intercept constant.

Precipitation concentration index (PCI)

This is an indicator of annual and seasonal trends in precipitation (Rawat *et al.*, 2021). An unbalanced distribution of precipitation can lead to periods of excessive rainfall or drought, making it difficult for plants and crops to grow (Michiels *et al.*, 1992). According to De Luis *et al.* (2011), the ICP is calculated as follows:

$$PCI = 100 * \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} p_i^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^{12} p_i)^2} \tag{4}$$

Where, $i=1, \dots, 12$ is the month (January, February,) ; p_i is the amount of rain in the i th month. It is interpreted in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Precipitation concentration index and interpretation

PCI values	Interpretation
$PCI < 10$	Uniform distribution of monthly rainfall over the year
$10 \leq PCI < 16$	Moderate distribution of monthly rainfall over the year
$16 \leq PCI < 20$	Irregular distribution of monthly rainfall over the year
$PCI > 20$	Distributions showing monthly rainfall variability over the year

Source: Michiels *et al.*, 1992

The primary data were analysed by looking at the frequency of gardeners' statements about smart strategies for coping with rainfall conditions and the food security status of gardeners in the study area. Commonly used methods to assess household food security status such as the Food Consumption Score (FCS), Dietary Diversity Score (DDS) and Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) were used in this study. Several other similar studies have been conducted in Ethiopia (Roba *et al.*, 2019; Ali *et al.*, 2022), Lesotho (Nkoko *et al.*, 2024) and Burma (Hanley *et al.*, 2021) using the same indices.

Dietary diversity score determination

The dietary diversity index is a qualitative measure of food consumption that provides an indication of the access of the household/individual to different types of foods and the nutritional adequacy of the household diet (FAO, 2011). The composition of the different food groups is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The food groups considered

Food groups	Foods in the group
Food group 1 (G1)	Cereals, roots and tubers, pulses
Food group 2 (G2)	Milk and dairy products
Food group 3 (G3)	Oils and fats
Food group 4 (G4)	Meat, fish, eggs and egg products
Food group 5 (G5)	Fruit and vegetables

Source: Hongbete *et al.*, 2017

The Dietary Diversity Score (DDS) is calculated by adding up the different foods consumed. The calculation involves assigning a score of 1 for consumption of a food

group and 0 for no consumption of a food group. The dietary diversity scale is thus as follows (Abegunde *et al.*, 2022): DDS is low if the score is 1, then DDS is medium if the score is between 4 and 6, and finally DDS is high if the score is 7. In the study, the Dietary Diversity Score (DDS) is considered low if the score is 1, medium if the score is 2 and high if the score is between 4 and 5.

Determination of the food consumption score (FCS)

This is a measure of food security based on three criteria: diversity, food frequency and relative nutritional importance of various food groups (Ndiaye, 2014). The household food consumption score (FCS) was calculated using the following formula (Ndiaye, 2014, Agalati and Yabi, 2017):

$$FCS = A_{Cereals} \times X_{Cereals} + A_{dried\ vegetables} \times X_{dried\ vegetables} + A_{vegetables} \times X_{vegetable} + A_{fruits} \times X_{fruits} + A_{milk} \times X_{milk} + A_{animal} \times X_{animal} + A_{sugar} \times X_{sugar} + A_{oils} \times X_{oils} \quad (5)$$

Where:

A_i = the weight assigned to the food group.

X_i = the number of days of consumption for each food group (≤ 7 days).

Table 4 shows the interpretation of the FCS.

Table 4. FCS values and interpretations

FCS values	Interpretation
$FCS < 21$	The household's food consumption is poor
$21 \leq FCS < 35$	Household food consumption is borderline
$35 \leq FCS < 45$	Household food consumption is moderately acceptable
$FCS \geq 45$	Consumption is acceptable

Source: Ndiaye, 2014

Experience of food insecurity scale

This is a measure based on self-reported perceptions or experiences of access to food at the individual or household level (Coates *et al.*, 2007). It has been used successfully in Nigeria (Ajani *et al.*, 2006) and Australia (Nolan *et al.*, 2006). In this study, it was measured on the basis of nine (09) questions and their frequency of occurrence over a one-month period, as in (Coates *et al.*, 2007):

1. Have you ever worried that your household didn't have enough food?

2. Have you or any member of your household been unable to eat the types of food you prefer because of a lack of resources?
3. Did you or any member of your household eat a limited variety of foods due to lack of resources?
4. Did you or any member of your household eat food that you did not want to eat because you did not have the resources to get other types of food?
5. Have you or any member of your household eaten a smaller meal than you would have liked because there was not enough food?
6. Did you or any member of your household eat fewer meals a day because there wasn't enough food?
7. Has the household ever gone without food completely because there was no money to buy it?
8. Have you or any member of your household ever gone to bed hungry because there wasn't enough food to eat?
9. Have you or any member of your household ever gone a whole day or night without eating because there was not enough food?

Experience of food insecurity was measured on a scale defined as rarely, sometimes, often and never (Table 5).

Table 5. Level of food insecurity assessment

Number	Scale	Food insecurity level
1	Often	↑
2	Sometimes	
3	Rarely	
4	Never	

Source: Coates *et al.*, 2007

Binary logistic regression

The logistic model is used to model the relationship between a dichotomous dependent variable and one or more independent variables, which may be continuous or binary (Rusliyadi *et al.*, 2023). In this context, therefore, the choice of each of the intelligent strategies used by the gardeners is a binary decision (0 or 1). The dependent variable is the adoption of smart strategies, with two modalities: adoption of smart strategies = 1 and non-adoption of smart strategies = 2. Thus, Y_i is defined in the following way:

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the } i\text{th producer has adopted a smart strategy} \\ 2 & \text{if producers have not adopted a smart strategy} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The hypothesis adopted in this study is that the choice of different smart strategies is influenced by the explanatory variables presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Explanatory variables and terms and conditions

Explanatory variables	Frequency	Modality	Expected sign
Age	Young=180 Old=12	1=Young 2=Old	+/-
Gender	Woman=73 Male=119	1=Woman 2=Male	+/-
Income level	Low income (0-300,000 fcfa/year)=100 High income (more than 2,000,000 fcfa/year)=92	1=Low income (0-300,000 fcfa/year) 2=High income (more than 2,000,000 fcfa/year)	+/-
Experience	Short experience (0-5 years)=62 Long experience (5-20 years)=130	1= Short experience (0-5 years) ; 2= Long experience (5-20 years)	+/-
Level of information about climate	Low level=52 High income=140	1=Low level 2=High level	+/-
Household size	Small (0-4 people)=103 Large (5-16 people)=89	1= Small size (0-4 people) 2=Tall (5-16 people)	+/-
Production area	Groundwater outcrops=150 Water table not at surface=42	1=Groundwater table outcrops 2=No groundwater outcrops	+/-

The relationship between the dependent variable and the independent or explanatory variables is expressed in Eq. (5) as:

$$Ln = \left(\frac{P_i}{(1-p)} \right) = \alpha + \beta_1 LnAge + \beta_2 LnGender + \beta_3 LnIncome level + \beta_4 LnExperience + \beta_5 Ln Level of information about climate + \beta_6 LnHousehold size + \beta_7 LnProduction area \quad (7)$$

Where, LnY=adoption of smart strategies (1=adopted, 2=not adopted).

- α =constant
- β_1 =regression coefficient (i=1, 2,...,5)
- LnAge=age
- LnGenre=gender
- Lnexperience=experience
- LnIncome level=income level

LnClimate information level=climate information
 LnHousehold size=household size
 Ln production area=production area.

Results and discussion

Characterization of rainfall variability in the study area

Fig. 2 below shows the variability of the annual precipitation totals, with an increasing trend over the period 1991-2021. The variability of cumulative precipitation is associated with a trend of alternating wet and dry periods over the period 2001-2021 (Fig. 3). However, the wet phase is more prolonged from 2005 to 2021. This phase is also highly variable.

Fig. 2. Variability and upward trend of the cumulative precipitation

Fig. 3. Dominance of the wet phase over the period 2001-2021

Fig. 4. Irregular distribution and high concentration of rainfall between 2001 and 2021.

The precipitation concentration index fluctuates during this period (Fig. 4). This confirms the results of Fig. 2 and 3. However, the PCIs are above 20 and sometimes even above 35 in the period 2006-2009. This means that the distribution of precipitation is irregular and concentrated in a few months of the year. This situation leads to an increase in extreme precipitation events (floods, droughts).

Climatic variability is a reality in the study area. This variability is exacerbated by a high concentration of precipitation. This situation can lead to more frequent droughts and floods. This has already been observed in other cities in Burkina Faso, such as Bobo-Dioulasso, Boromo, Koudougou, Ouahigouya and Gaoua (Yanogo and Yaméogo, 2023; Yaméogo, 2024). Several other authors, such as Yaméogo and Rouamba, 2023, and Koala *et al.*, 2023 in Burkina Faso, agree with the above authors. They add that this trend in variability and the increase in extreme precipitation will continue until 2050.

Smart strategies in vegetable production and food security

The current rainfall pattern, which is variable, irregular and concentrated over a few months, makes vegetable production very difficult. This forces farmers to adapt to the characteristics of rainfall. This is why intelligent systems have been introduced in all the vegetable plots in sector 9 of Réo. Will these intelligent strategies have an impact on the farmers' food situation?

Range of smart strategies used by market gardeners in market garden plots

Faced with the change in rainfall patterns, market gardeners have opted for several smart strategies to adapt to this new climatic situation, using strategies such as growing leafy vegetables, adopting short-cycle vegetables and combining several species with vegetables in market garden plots.

Growing leafy vegetables

Celery, mint and parsley production has become the main production system on 70% of the plots in sector

9 of Réo (Fig. 5). This is due to the unusual drop in groundwater levels in the region over the last ten years. Leafy vegetables require less water than onions and tomatoes. The option for these vegetables is to make rational use of groundwater resources.

Fig. 5. Plots of celery and parsley in sector 9 of Réo (shot: Yaméogo, December 2023)

Celery associated with mango trees in January 2024 in sector 9 of Réo
Mint combined with parsley and maize in December 2023 in sector 9 of the town of Réo

Fig. 6. Associations of maize, celery and mint with vegetables in the two study areas

Growing short-cycle vegetables

Vegetable production is affected by rainfall conditions in the region. Growers are also turning to short-cycle seeds for vegetable production. For example, 50% of them use

short-cycle onion seed to adapt to the reduced number of rainy days during the rainy season.

Multi-species planting combinations in market garden plots

Rainfall is associated with high wind speeds. Market gardeners therefore plant citrus, papaya and mango trees to reduce wind speeds in their plots (Fig. 6).

Several other species are introduced by market gardeners and their number varies according to the size of the market garden plots (Table 7). The table shows that *Mangifera indica* dominates the plots (52.10%), followed by *Carica papaya* (20.83%) and *Zea mays* (15.62%). Species such as *Citrus limon*, *Musa x paradisiaca* and *Bombax costatum* are not very present in the plots.

Table 7. Main species present in market garden plots

	Types of species in the plot	Plot size	f	%
Sector 9 of the town of Réo	<i>Zea mays</i>	0.5ha	30	15.62 %
	<i>Carica papaya</i>	0.75ha	40	20.83 %
	<i>Musa x paradisiaca</i>	0.75ha	10	5.21 %
	<i>Citrus limon</i>	1.25ha	10	5.21 %
	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	1.5ha	100	52.10 %
	<i>Bombax costatum</i>	0.25ha	2	1.04 %

f = Frequency, %= Percentage

Source: Field surveys, December 2023-February 2024

Table 8. Significant influence of explanatory variables on the adoption of different smart strategies

	Growing leafy vegetables						
	B	E.S	Wald	ddl	Sig.	Exp(B)	
Age	-1.001	0.370	7.339	1	0.007	0.367	
Gender	-1.724	0.527	10.697	1	0.001	0.178	
Level of education	-0.372	0.898	0.171	1	0.679	0.689	
Size of household	-0.003	0.533	.000	1	0.995	0.997	
Experience	0.600	0.352	2.908	1	0.088	1.822	
Income earned	-1.466	0.461	10.102	1	0.001	0.231	
Constant	5.743	1.750	10.776	1	0.001	312.015	
Combining several species in market garden plots							
	B	E. S	Wald	ddl	Sig.	Exp(B)	
Age	-0.771	.429	3.221	1	0.073	0.463	
Gender	2.484	.658	14.244	1	0.000	11.987	
Level of education	-1.824	1.308	1.944	1	0.163	0.161	
Size of household	-1.331	.671	3.931	1	0.047	0.264	
Experience	-0.309	.466	0.439	1	0.508	0.734	
Income earned	-2.961	0.541	29.937	1	0.000	0.052	
Production area	-1.086	.458	5.619	1	0.018	0.338	
The adoption of short-cycle vegetables							
	B	E.S	Wald	ddl	Sig.	Exp(B)	
Age	0.460	0.353	1.698	1	0.193	1.584	
Gender	1.607	0.556	8.360	1	0.004	4.986	
Level of education	-.949	0.932	1.038	1	0.308	.387	
Size of household	0.348	0.560	0.387	1	0.534	1.417	

Experience	-1.810	0.504	12.919	1	0.000	0.164
Income earned	-.059	0.370	0.025	1	0.874	0.943
Production area	0.980	0.400	5.993	1	0.014	2.665
Constant	0.009	1.878	.000	1	0.996	1.009

Source: Field surveys, December 2023-February 2024

Gardeners in sector 9 of the town of Réo have mobilised various intelligent strategies to deal with the climate. In the peri-urban area of Nidialpoun, in the commune of Réo, Burkina Faso, market gardeners also use a number of strategies, such as increasing the number of wells to cope with the recurrence of droughts, using compost to fertilise the soil, and integrating other species such as lemons and especially papaya into market garden plots (Yaméogo *et al.*, 2022). In Ethiopia, several other strategies such as crop diversification, irrigation, drought-tolerant and early-maturing crop varieties, integrated soil fertility management and integrated pest management have been used as practices to improve crop productivity (Erekalo *et al.*, 2023).

Factors influencing the adoption of different smart strategies in the city of Réo

The regression of the two variables showed that explanatory variables such as gender, income level, production zone and experience had a different influence on the adoption of smart strategies in the zone (Table 8).

This table shows that gender, income and experience influence the decision to grow leafy vegetables (celery, mint and parsley). More men than women grow vegetable crops. This means that few women adopt the strategies as they play a supporting role to their husbands. This has led to a differentiated adoption of the strategies. The level of income also has an impact on the adoption of strategies, as these people lose a lot of financial resources as a result of losses caused by droughts, high temperatures and floods. As a result, they are more likely to adopt strategies to avoid financial losses, in contrast to those who grow for subsistence. The experience of market gardeners also motivates them to adopt smart strategies, as

they have already experienced climatic and economic problems. They are proactive rather than passive. They anticipate potential difficulties in vegetable production. The strategy of intercropping in vegetable plots is influenced by gender, household size, income level and production area. In fact, men are the landowners in the study area and therefore the only ones with the right to plant fruit species. However, women cannot necessarily plant them on their plots. This may lead to a difference in the use of this strategy. The adoption of short-cycle vegetables is also influenced by gender, experience and production area.

These results are also in line with those of Anuga *et al.* 2022 in Ghana. The latter found that farmers' willingness to adopt smart strategies was driven by the climate crisis as well as other factors such as increased yield/productivity, technical knowledge and understanding of practices, risk aversion, fear and gender. Ogisi *et al.*, 2023 note that the adoption of climate-smart strategies is multi-factorial (climate, agricultural and economic factors, socio-psychological factors, institutional factors).

Impact of smart strategies on food security for market garden producers

Smart strategies and dietary diversity for market gardeners

The introduction of smart strategies to cope with rainfall variability has brought benefits in terms of dietary diversity (Fig. 7). Dietary diversity is high for 86% of the gardeners because they eat leafy vegetables (parsley, mint), flowers (red kapok flowers) especially during the holidays, and cereals, especially maize, and fruits (papaya, mango, lemon) throughout the year. The dietary diversity score for the five (05) food groups is 4 (Table 9).

Fig. 7. Diversité alimentaire élevée chez les maraichers urbains

Fig. 8. High level of food consumption among market gardeners

Table 9. The main types of food consumed by market gardeners

Food groups	Foods in the group	Consumed by market gardeners	Frequency of consumption (%)	Score
Food group 1 (G1)	Cereals, roots and tubers, pulses	Maize, rice Beans	90 40	1
Food group 2 (G2)	Milk and dairy products	-	0	0
Food group 3 (G3)	Oils and fats	Oil	70	1
Food group 4 (G4)	Meat, fish, eggs and egg products	Pork meat Mutton Fish	60 40 70	1
Food group 5 (G5)	Fruit and vegetables	Mango Papaya Lemon Banana Aubergine Onion Tomato Cabbage Parsley Mint	90 50 90 40 80 90 90 60 40 50	1
Total				4

Source: field surveys, 2023-2024

Table 10. High level of food consumption by market gardeners

Food	Food consumed by market gardeners and their families	Food groups	Weighting (A)	Number of days consumed in the last 7 days (B)	Score (A*B)
Sorghum, rice, maize, millet	Sorghum, rice, maize, millet	Cereals and tubers	2	7	14
Cassava, potatoes and sweet potatoes	-	Dried vegetables	3	4	12
beans, peas, groundnuts	Beans, groundnuts	Vegetables	1	7	7
Vegetables, condiments, leafy vegetables	Eggplant, mint, parsley, onion, tomato, cabbage	Fruit	5	4	8
fruit	Mango, papaya, limon, banana	Meat and fish	7	3	12
Beef, goat, poultry, eggs, pork and fish	Pork meat, fish	Milk	4	0	0
Milk, yoghurt and other dairy products	-	Sugar	0,5	3	1,5
Sugar and sweet products	Honey and sugar	Oil	0,5	7	3,5
Oil/fats	Shea butter and oil sold in shops				79
FCS					

Source: Source: Field surveys, December 2023

Table 11. Low level of food insecurity among market gardeners

	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1. Have you ever worried that your household didn't have enough food?	5 2.60%	6 3.13%	100 52.08%	81 42.19%
2. Have you or any member of your household been unable to eat the types of food you prefer because of a lack of resources?	8 4.17%	10 5.21%	90 46.88%	84 43.75%
3. Did you or any member of your household eat a limited variety of foods due to lack of resources?	4 2.08%	15 7.81%	73 38.02%	100 52.08%
4. Did you or any member of your household eat food that you did not want to eat because you did not have the resources to get other types of food?	2.00 1.04%	10.00 5.21%	95.00 49.48%	85.00 44.27%
5. Have you or any member of your household eaten a smaller meal than you would have liked because there was not enough food?	4 2.08%	6 3.13%	82 42.71%	100 52.08%
6. Did you or any member of your household eat fewer meals per day because there wasn't enough food?	0 0%	8 4.17%	70 36.46%	114 59.38%
7. Has the household ever gone without food completely because there was no money to buy it?	0 0%	0 0%	100 52.08%	92 47.92%
8. Have you or any member of your household ever gone to bed hungry because there wasn't enough food to eat?	0 0%	1 0.52%	70 36.46%	121 63.02%
9. Have you or any member of your household ever gone a whole day or night without eating because there was not enough food?	0 0%	0 0%	57 29.69%	135 70.31%

Source: Field surveys, December 2023-February 2024

Smart strategies and food consumption for market gardeners

Gardeners produce several species on their plots, which gives them a variety of food options. This situation has led to an increase in the FCS of market gardeners (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 shows that 87% of market gardeners have acceptable food security, as they and their families consume a wide range of foods (Table 10). This situation shows that the smart strategies adopted by the gardeners enable them to consume food on a regular basis. Table 10 shows the food consumption of the market gardeners and their families over the course of a week to give a better idea of the frequency of food consumption.

The results on the improvement of the food situation of market gardeners in sector 9 of the town of Réo are in line with the work of other authors using the same methods to assess food security. In fact, farmers in West Africa, particularly in Benin, Mali and Nigeria, who mobilised several strategies increased their food consumption score, in contrast to those who used one smart strategy (Tabe-Ojong *et al.*, 2023). The same observations were made by Belay *et al.* 2023 and Huluka *et al.*, 2019 in Ethiopia, and Abegunde *et al.*, 2022 in

South Africa. In fact, households that adopt smart strategies have richer diets than those that do not.

Smart strategies and food insecurity at the level of market gardeners

The Food Insecurity Access Scale was used to assess levels of food insecurity. More than 80% of market gardener households reported that all 9 questions had rarely or never been asked (Table 11). This means that more than 80% of market gardeners are food security.

Conclusion

Rainfall variability has forced market gardeners to implement intelligent strategies to adapt to the new climatic situation. This has led to the production of leafy vegetables, the combination of several species in the plots and the introduction of short-cycle vegetables such as onions. These different strategies, used simultaneously by market gardeners, have increased the food security of market gardeners in the town of Réo. It is therefore important that the authorities in the town of Réo encourage gardeners by training them in the use of natural compost, and providing micro-credits to gardeners could also help to spread smart strategies, especially among women.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the market gardeners in the town of Réo for their willingness to answer our questions in order to ensure the success of this study.

References

- Abegunde VO, Sibanda M, Obi A.** 2022. Effect of climate-smart agriculture on household food security in small-scale production systems: A micro-level analysis from South Africa. *Cogent Social Sciences* **8(1)**, 2086343.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2022.2086343>
- Agalati B, Yabi JA.** 2017. Déterminants de la sécurité alimentaire des ménages des terroirs riverains des zones cynégétiques des aires protégées du Nord-Bénin. *Annales de l'Université de Parakou, Série « Sciences Naturelles et Agronomie » Hors-serie* **1**, 82-91.
- Agarwal T, Goel PA, Gartaula H, Rai M, Bijarniya D, Rahut DB, Jat ML.** 2022. Gendered impacts of climate-smart agriculture on household food security and labor migration: Insights from Bihar, India. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management* **14(1)**, 1-19.
- Ajani SR, Adebukola BC, Oyindamola YB.** 2006. Measuring household food insecurity in selected local government areas of Lagos and Ibadan, Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* **5(1)**, 62-67.
- Ali H, Menza M, Hagos F, Hailelassie A.** 2022. Impact of climate-smart agriculture adoption on food security and multidimensional poverty of rural farm households in the Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Agriculture & Food Security* **11(1)**, 1-16.
- Anuga SW, Fosu-Mensah BY, Nukpezah D, Ahenkan A, Gordon C, Baye RS.** 2022. Climate-smart agriculture: Greenhouse gas mitigation in climate-smart villages of Ghana. *Environmental Sustainability* **5(4)**, 457-469.
- Atılgan A, Tanrıverdi C, Yücel A, Öz H, Degirmenci H.** 2017. Analysis of long-term temperature data using Mann-Kendall trend test and linear regression methods: The case of the Southeastern Anatolia Region. *Scientific Papers. Series A. Agronomy* **LX**, 455-462.
- Balram P, Fanal L.** 2020. Meteorological drought assessment using standardized precipitation index for different agro-climatic zones of Odisha. *Mausam* **71(3)**, 467-480.
- Belay A, Mirzabaev A, Recha JW, Oludhe C, Osano PM, Berhane Z, Solomon D.** 2023. Does climate-smart agriculture improve household income and food security? Evidence from Southern Ethiopia. *Environment, Development and Sustainability* **1-28**.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-03307-9>
- Coates J, Swindale A, Bilinsky P.** 2007. Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) for measurement of food access: Indicator guide. Washington, DC: FANTA (Food and Nutrition Technical Assistance), FHI 360, p. 36.
- El-Geziry TM.** 2022. Analysis of air temperature trends as a climate change indicator for Alexandria (Egypt). *Athens Journal of Sciences* **9**, 239-256.
<https://doi.org/10.30958/ajs.9-4-2>
- Erekalo KT, Yadda TA.** 2023. Climate-smart agriculture in Ethiopia: Adoption of multiple crop production practices as sustainable adaptation and mitigation strategies. *World Development Sustainability* **3**, 100099.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wds.2023.100099>
- FAO (Food and Agricultural Organization).** 2011. Guidelines for measuring household and individual dietary diversity. Prepared by Kennedy G, Ballard T, Dop M. FAO, p. 56.

- Finizola e Silva M, Van Schoubroeck S, Cools J, Van Passel S.** 2024. A systematic review identifying the drivers and barriers to the adoption of climate-smart agriculture by smallholder farmers in Africa. *Frontiers in Environmental Economics* **3**, 1356335.
- Hasan MK, Desiere S, D'Haese M, Kumar L.** 2018. Impact of climate-smart agriculture adoption on the food security of coastal farmers in Bangladesh. *Food Security* **10**, 1073-1088.
- Hongbete F, Kindossi JM, Bio Bone B, Akissoe N, Hounhouigan JD, Nago MC.** 2017. Evolution des habitudes alimentaires des Baatonu au Nord Bénin. *Annales de l'Université de Parakou, Série « Sciences Naturelles et Agronomie » Hors-serie* **1**, 92-99.
- Huluka AT, Wondimagegnhu BA.** 2019. Determinants of household dietary diversity in the Yayo biosphere reserve of Ethiopia: An empirical analysis using the sustainable livelihood framework. *Cogent Food & Agriculture* **5(1)**, 1690829. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2019.1690829>
- IPCC.** 2021. Summary for policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte V, Zhai P, Pirani A, Connors SL, Péan C, Berger S, Caud N, Chen Y, Goldfarb L, Gomis MI, Huang M, Leitzell K, Lonnoy E, Matthews JBR, Maycock TK, Waterfield T, Yelekçi O, Yu R, Zhou B (eds.)]. In Press, p. 40.
- IPCC.** 2022. Annex II: Glossary [Möller V, van Diemen R, Matthews JBR, Méndez C, Semenov S, Fuglestedt JS, Reisinger A (eds.)]. In: *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Pörtner HO, Roberts DC, Tignor M, Poloczanska ES, Mintenbeck K, Alegría A, Craig M, Langsdorf S, Lösschke S, Möller V, Okem A, Rama B (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, 2897-2930. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.029>
- Kharisma V, Abe N.** 2020. Food insecurity and associated socioeconomic factors: Application of Rasch and binary logistic models with household survey data in three megacities in Indonesia. *Social Indicators Research* **148(2)**, 655-679.
- Koala S, Nakoulma G, Dipama JM.** 2023. Évolution des précipitations et de la température à l'horizon 2050 avec les modèles climatiques CMIP5 dans le bassin versant du Nakambé (Burkina Faso). *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT)* **37(2)**, 110-124.
- Lüning S, Galka M, Danladi IB, Adagunodo TA, Vahrenholt F.** 2018. Hydroclimate in Africa during the medieval climate anomaly. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* **495**, 309-322.
- McKee TB, Doesken NJ, Kleist J.** 1993. The relationship of drought frequency and duration to time scales. In: *Proceedings of the 8th Conference on Applied Climatology* **17(22)**, 179-183.
- Michiels P, Gabriels D, Hartmann R.** 1992. Using the seasonal and temporal precipitation concentration index for characterizing the monthly rainfall distribution in Spain. *Catena* **19(1)**, 43-58. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0341-8162\(92\)90016-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0341-8162(92)90016-5)
- Ndiaye M.** 2014. Food security indicators, integrating nutrition and food security programs in emergency situations and for building resilience. *Regional Training Workshop, 10-12 Juin 2014 Afrique de l'Ouest/Sahel – Saly, Sénégal*, p. 24.
- Ndung'u S, Ogema V, Thiga M, Wandahwa P.** 2023. Factors influencing the adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices among smallholder farmers in Kakamega County, Kenya. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development* **23(10)**, 24759-24782.
- Nkoko N, Cronje N, Swanepoel JW.** 2024. Factors associated with food security among smallholder farming households in Lesotho. *Agriculture & Food Security* **13(1)**, 1-10.

- Nolan M, Rikard-Bell G, Mohsin M, Williams M.** 2006. Food insecurity in three socially disadvantaged localities in Sydney, Australia. *Health Promotion Journal of Australia* **17(3)**, 247-253.
- Ogisi OD, Begho T.** 2023. Adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices in sub-Saharan Africa: A review of the progress, barriers, gender differences, and recommendations. *Farming System* **1(2)**, 100019.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.farsys.2023.100019>
- Panthou G, Vischel T, Lebel T.** 2014. Recent trends in the regime of extreme rainfall in the Central Sahel. *International Journal of Climatology* **34(15)**, 3998-4006. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.3984>
- Rawat KS, Pa RK, Singh SK.** 2021. Rainfall variability analysis using Precipitation Concentration Index: A case study of the western agro-climatic zone of Punjab, India. *The Indonesian Journal of Geography* **53(3)**, 388-399.
- Roba KT, O'Connor TP, O'Brien NM, Aweke CS, Kahsay ZA, Chisholm N, Lahiff E.** 2019. Seasonal variations in household food insecurity and dietary diversity and their association with maternal and child nutritional status in rural Ethiopia. *Food Security* **11**, 651-664.
- Rouamba S, Yaméogo J, Sanou K, Zongo R, Yanogo IP.** 2023. Trends and variability of extreme climate indices in the Boucle du Mouhoun (Burkina Faso). *GEOREVIEW: Scientific Annals of Stefan cel Mare University of Suceava. Geography Series* **33(1)**, 70-84.
<https://doi.org/10.4316/GEOREVIEW.2023.01.07>
- Rusliyadi M, Ardi YWY, Winarno K.** 2023. Binary logistics regression model to analyze factors influencing technology adoption process vegetable farmers case in Central Java Indonesia. In: *Proceedings of the International Symposium Southeast Asia Vegetable*, 460-470.
- Salman M, Haque S, Hossain ME, Zaman N, Hira FTZ.** 2023. Pathways toward the sustainable improvement of food security: adopting the household food insecurity access scale in rural farming households in Bangladesh. *Research in Globalization* **7**, 100172.
- Shani FK, Joshua M, Ngongondo C.** 2014. Determinants of smallholder farmers' adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices in Zomba, Eastern Malawi. *Sustainability* **16(9)**, 3782.
- Sougué M, Merz B, Sogbedji JM, Zougmore F.** 2023. Extreme rainfall in southern Burkina Faso, West Africa: trends and links to Atlantic Sea surface temperature. *Atmosphere* **14(2)**, 284.
- Sylla MB, Nikiema PM, Gibba P, Kebe I, Klutse NAB.** 2016. Climate change over West Africa: recent trends and future projection. Adaptation to climate change and variability in rural West Africa. In: Yaro J., Hesselberg J. (eds) *Adaptation to Climate Change and Variability in Rural West Africa*. Springer, Cham, 25-40.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31499-0_3
- Tabe-Ojong PJ, Martin, Aihounton GB, Lokossou JC.** 2023. Climate-smart agriculture and food security: cross-country evidence from West Africa. *Global Environmental Change* **81**, 102697.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2023.102697>
- Tilahun G, Bantider A, Yayeh D.** 2023. Analyzing the impact of climate-smart agriculture on household welfare in subsistence mixed farming system: evidence from Geshy Watershed, Southwest Ethiopia. *Global Social Welfare* **10(3)**, 235-247.
- Yaméogo J, Ndoutorlengar M, Rouamba S.** 2022. Perceptions of climate risks, socio-environmental impacts and adaptation strategies: the case of market gardeners in the lowlands of Nédialpoun, Zoula Village (Burkina Faso). *IIARD International Journal of Geography and Environmental Management* **8(2)**, 20-35.
<https://doi.org/10.56201/ijgem.v8.n02.2022.pg20.35>

- Yaméogo J, Rouamba S, Sanou K, Zongo R, Yanogo PI.** 2023. Perception of extreme climatic events on bananas around the Petit Balè Dam in the Boromo Commune (Burkina Faso). *European Journal of Science, Innovation and Technology* **3(4)**, 209-223.
- Yaméogo J, Sawadogo A.** 2024. Consequences of precipitation variability and socio-economic activity on surface water in the Vranso Water Basin (Burkina Faso). *Glasnik Srpskog Geografskog Društva* **104(1)**, 255-266. <https://doi.org/10.2298/gsgd2401255y>
- Yaméogo J, Yanogo PI.** 2023. Assessment of climate change adaptation strategies in developing countries: the case of Burkina Faso. *Journal of Innovations and Sustainability* **7(2)**, 1-32.
- Yaméogo J.** 2024. Trends and forecasts of extreme precipitation indices in three cities of Burkina Faso: between a non-parametric statistical analysis and Holt-Winters Smoothing Method. *Discover Atmosphere*, 2024 (In press).
- Yanogo IP, Yaméogo J.** 2023. Recent rainfall trends between 1990 and 2020: contrasting characteristics between two climate zones in Burkina Faso (West Africa). *Glasnik Srpskog Geografskog Društva* **103(1)**, 87-106. <https://doi.org/10.2298/GSGD2301087Y>
- Yanogo PI.** 2023. Rainfall variability and changes in market gardening systems: a case study in Réo (mid-west region of Burkina Faso). *Present Environment & Sustainable Development* **17(2)**, 213-228. <https://doi.org/10.47743/pesd2023172016>
- Zelege G, Teshome M, Ayele L.** 2024. Determinants of smallholder farmers' decisions to use multiple climate-smart agricultural technologies in North Wello Zone, Northern Ethiopia. *Sustainability* **16(11)**, 4560.
- Zhang Q, Berntell E, Li Q, Ljungqvist FC.** 2021. Understanding the variability of the rainfall dipole in West Africa using the EC-Earth last millennium simulation. *Climate Dynamics* **57(1)**, 93-107.